

ISic3710

I.Sicily inscription 3710

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Camarina

Place of origin (modern)

Kamarina

Provenance

contrada Piombo, localita Bellaccio, rescue excavation by G. Di Stefano (undated), area of aa small necropolis

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Camarina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Di Stefano, G. 2013. Camarina. Le acquisizioni, il museo tematico, la collezione "Biagio Pace", il lapidario. Ispica. At 30 ph

Copani, Fabio 2014. Un esercizio di scrittura su una stele da Contrada Piombo (Camarina). In Alfieri Tonini, Teresa, Struffolino, Stefano(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*.

Trento. pp. 197-201.

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